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CASCADING THE EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND PERFORMANCE FOR INSTRUCTION VITALITY

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Abstract: This research aims to determine the level of emotional intelligence and performance of teachers in the identified public elementary schools. Based on the findings, it can be noted that teachers have strong motivation and willingness as perceived by the administrators, and among all aspects of emotional intelligence, administrators perceived that teacher have enough self-management that dealt in times of difficulties. Moreover, teachers' performance on the identified 5 key areas were very satisfactory, thus, it is a strong predictor of teacher's awareness on their level of intelligence. Overall, finding suggest that although teachers have high level of emotional intelligence, low self-regulation and lack of accountability were seen as one of the teachers' weaknesses. By recognizing the results of this study, the overall findings suggest that emotional intelligence has a specific buffering effect affecting intrapersonal and interpersonal processes.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, learners' performance, Instructional Vitality

1. Introduction

Education is vital in producing a superior manpower of the country, which the country's essential tool in making its economy more stable and sustaining. The educational world is the main school - the alternative institutions for educational services. Inside the school are the teachers who play significant roles in the life and education of the learners (Baytiyeh, 2018). They are the persons in responsible on skills development of the learners. Likewise, in preparing them physically, and developing them mentally.

On the other hand, the teacher performances in school have an important role for achieving the goals of school, which could be affected by many factors, both of internal and external (Andriani et al., 2018). Teachers are professional educators with the

primary duty is educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluating the students on childhood early education, formal education, basic education, and secondary education (Law, No. 14, 2005).

However, fact is undeniable that Philippine educational system is still far behind from those of western countries (Musa & Ziatdinov, 2012; Symaco & Tee, 2019). The quality of education Filipino pupils receive could somehow be judged as only enough to develop skills necessary for the local job market. But compared to most Asian or western counterparts, Filipino learners lag behind when it comes to real world applications of the knowledge learned in schools. Generally, Filipino learners' abilities do not match with that of other pupils in other countries, especially Western countries. Latest international educational evaluations show that there is a need to improve Filipino learners' performance. In all of the tests of the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) conducted by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), Filipino students' performances fall behind most student's outcome from other countries in both mathematics and science subjects.

Analysis of these dismal results showed that Filipino students were poorly equipped when it comes to comprehension or analysis of the problems. One of the reasons for this poor performance is the lack of necessary training in using higher order thinking in problem solving. Filipino students are not used to this kind of thinking as most teachers are not skilled enough or do not possess the necessary skills to develop critical thinking ability among the students. Analysis of the evaluation results also implied that generally, Filipino teachers are not effective enough.

Whereas, successful teaching does not only require the subject knowledge, but it is also needing the effective skills (Margot & Kettler, 2019). According to Goleman (1995), successful teaching is the combination of thinking and feeling, in which those skills are the emotional intelligence. The emotional intelligence is better known as a useful tool for improving the quality of life and the people performance within work (Miao, et al., 2018). Teachers, as professionals who work within human development area, being responsible for the becoming of many generations of children, need to demonstrate real emotional qualities which could enable them for a better performing (Palmer, 2017).

There are many conceptualization within the literature, the emotional intelligence viewed as intelligence (it describes an emotional general aptitude so it can be conceived as an equivalent intelligence quotient) (the model of Mayer & Salovey); the emotional intelligence viewed as a trait (Petrides, K.V & Furnham, A , 2001) (it offers a better understanding for the way the person filters and directs the emotional aptitudes); the emotional intelligence as a sum of learned competences (it allows the examination of the adjustment way of the person and it can be seen as a performance) (the Bar-On model).

It is emphasized that the trait emotional intelligence differs from the emotional intelligence ability and the differences are based on the measurement way (Pérez, J. C., Petrides, K. V., & Furnham, 2005) (the former construct comprises behavioral dispositions linked to the emotions and self-perceived abilities which are measured through self-report and the last is defined through the cognitive abilities related to the emotions which are measured through maximum-performance tests).

According to Bafadal (2003), there are eight things to be desired by the teacher accordingly performance can be improved naturally. Those are feel safe and good manners, the work conditions are wish, participation, fairness and honesty, poisoned, recognition, and appreciation for donate, join with a policy that school made, the

opportunity to develop self-respecting. Lower quality of education can't be separated from the role of the teacher as a main manager of the educational process in addition the other factors, such as the quality and characteristics input, the environment and infrastructure (Blazely, 1997).

While, according to Martinis and Maisah (2010) factors that make performance include intrinsic factors (personal/individual) or human resources and extrinsic is the leadership, system, team, and situational. Teacher competence needs carrying out of the teaching duties in schools. According Barlow (1985) stated that the teacher competence is the ability of teacher responsibility to show his or her duties appropriately. Wade and Moor (1992) stated that teachers need pedagogical knowledge and training to develop themselves as a teacher proficient confident of their own abilities and faith in the potential students. To make high quality learners, teacher must be the master of four competences. All of competences must be capable to improve the teachers' teaching performance.

Teachers are the backbone of the educational institutions, without teachers, these institutes are considered the body without soul. According to National Education Report, the trained teachers are essential for the education system. The teachers who got training can be expected have the highly knowledge of emotional intelligence. Definitely the teachers having good emotional intelligence can teach the students in effective manner. But it is needed to measure these phenomena, at what level the emotional intelligence can plays its role in learning process.

Emotional intelligence is the ability for recognizing our own feelings and the feelings to each other's the ability to manage the emotion better in ourselves and relationship to the others (Hamzah, 2005). It can be said that the teachers have good emotional intelligence is the teacher who have the ability to manage the emotions and feelings, as well as more active in cooperation for achieving educational goals. Robert Rosenthal in his research indicates that people who can able to analyses feelings and non- verbal code are better to adjust themselves emotionally, more popular, easier to interact, and more sensitive (Goleman, 2006). In the learning process, emotional intelligence of teachers is needed, by Mulyasa (2006) so that why learning take place optimally and improve to the maximum learning. There are several ways to develop emotional intelligence in learning that provides a conducive environment, makes a democratic learning situation, empathy, and perceived by the students, helps the students find a solution in any problems that may they get, engages the students optimally in learning, physically, socially, and emotionally, responds to all of student's positive behaviors, and avoids the negative response, gives the example for obeying the rules and discipline learning.

According to Goleman (2006), emotional intelligence is the ability to regulate emotional life with intelligence (to manage our emotional life with intelligence); to maintain the emotional with harmony and disclosure (the appropriateness of emotion and expression) through the self-awareness skills, self-control, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills. Emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize feelings, reach and build feelings to help the idea, feelings and understanding are meaning and dept feeling control that fosters emotional and intellectual (Stein & Book, 2002). Emotional intelligence can be said to cover five main areas: self-awareness, emotional control, self-motivation, empathy and relationship skills. It is, of course, important for good communication with others – and is therefore a gateway to better learning, friendships, academic success and employment.

There are different antecedents of good quality of education in which the teaching methodology, emotional awareness of the teachers, self-confidence, conflict

management, discipline management, class management, lesson planning etc. So, it is clear that for a good quality of education, it is also necessary the teachers have all the knowledge, about their subject and teaching methodology, and specific skills like as emotional intelligence. The researcher deemed it necessary to verify the emotional intelligence status of the teachers, for it really plays a big factor on their teaching performance in terms of teaching-learning process, students' outcomes, and community involvement, hence this study.

2. Purpose of the Study

This research determined the level of emotional intelligence and performance of teachers in the identified public elementary schools. Moreover, it addressed the following level of emotional intelligence of the teachers: self-Awareness, social Awareness, self-management and relationship management. It also includes the overall performance of the respondents based on IPCR.

3. Research Methodology

The descriptive method of research was used in this study, which described data and the characteristics of the population under study. This method answered the questions who, what, where, when, and how. In particular, the present conditions of the respondents as regards to the level of emotional intelligence and performance of teachers in the identified public elementary schools. Data will be described and analyzed through data gathered using the research instrument. The respondents of the study were the teachers and administrators. This study focusses in basic education, the instrument used in this study was already passed through a process of validity and reliability measures, since it was already used to conduct study on emotional intelligence of the school heads by Miscreola (2012) in the local setting. Hence, further validation is considered no longer necessary. Questionnaires were retrieved and data was collated. Data and information with regards to the study was treated with utmost confidence.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Motivation and Willingness

Motivation and Willingness	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	4.48	SA	4.27	SA
On the whole, I'm pleased with my life.	4.16	A	4.4	SA
I generally believe that things will work out fine in my life.	3.84	A	4.01	A
I expect that I will do well on most things in I try.	3.92	A	4.67	SA
When I am faced with challenge, I don't easily give up because I believe I will not fail.	4.32	SA	4.27	SA
Total	4.14	SA	4.34	SA

Table 1 presents the data in terms of Motivation and willingness. Data shows that the statement refers to I feel that I have a number of good qualities got the highest weighted mean of 4.48 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to, I generally believe that things will work out fine in my life got the lowest weighted mean of 3.84 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other

hand, the statement refers to I expect that I will do well on most things in I try got the highest weighted mean of 4.67 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to, I generally believe that things will work out fine in my life got the lowest weighted mean of 4.01 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that respondents have high motivation and willingness to work in times of pandemic.

Table 2. Social Awareness

Social-awareness	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I don't find any difficulty to see things from another person's viewpoint.	4.08	A	4.28	SA
I'm normally able to "get into someone's shoes" and experience their emotions.	4.14	A	4.57	SA
In my group of friends, I am generally aware of how each person feels about the people in our social circle.	4.1	A	4.50	SA
I find it time to listen to other person's problems.	4.28	SA	4.29	SA
My co-workers easily confide on me.	4.06	A	4.52	SA
Total	4.13	A	4.44	SA

Table 2 presents the data in terms of Social-awareness. Data shows that the statement refers to I find it time to listen to other person's problems got the highest weighted mean of 4.28 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to, my co-workers easily confide on me got the lowest weighted mean of 4.06 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to I'm normally able to "get into someone's shoes" and experience their emotions got the highest weighted mean of 4.57 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to, I don't find any difficulty to see things from another person's viewpoint got the lowest weighted mean of 4.28 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators have strong social awareness that makes them productive.

Table 3. Self-management

Self-Management	Teachers		administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I don't find any difficulty to regulate my emotions.	3.82	A	4.7	SA
I don't change my mind frequently.	4.02	A	4.52	SA
I'm usually able to find ways to control my emotions when I want to.	4.18	A	4.61	SA
On the whole, I am able to deal with stress.	4.22	SA	4.44	SA
I pray/meditate to shake off bad mood.	3.98	A	4.58	SA
Total	4.04	A	4.57	SA

Table 3 presents the data in terms of Self-Management. Data shows that the statement refers to on the whole, I am able to deal with stress got the highest weighted mean of 4.22 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to, I don't find any difficulty to regulate my emotions got the lowest weighted mean of 3.82 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to I don't find any difficulty to regulate my emotions got the highest weighted mean of 4.7 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to on the whole, I am able to deal with stress got the lowest weighted mean of 4.44 which verbally

described as strongly agree. This indicates that respondents don't find any difficulty to regulate emotions and they can handle difficult situations.

Table 4. Relationship Management

Relationship Management	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I can deal effectively with people.	4.22	SA	4.52	SA
I usually able to influence the way other people feel.	4.44	SA	4.54	SA
I would describe myself as a good "negotiator".	4.16	A	4.4	SA
My fellow workers want me to share in their celebrations.	4.14	A	4.39	SA
I find it easy to approach a fellow worker and ask how she is doing.	4.38	SA	4.61	SA
Total	4.268	SA	4.492	SA

Table 4 presents the data in terms of Relationship Management. Data shows that the statement refers to I usually able to influence the way other people feel highest weighted mean of 4.44 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to, my fellow workers want me to share in their celebrations got the lowest weighted mean of 4.14 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, I find it easy to approach a fellow worker and ask how s/he is doing got the highest weighted mean of 4.61 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to My fellow workers want me to share in their celebrations got the lowest weighted mean of 4.39 which verbally described as strongly agree. This indicates that respondents can deal effectively with people.

Table 5. Teachers Performance

Teachers Performance	Ratings
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	VS
Learning Environment	VS
Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, & Assessment and Reporting	VS
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development	VS

Table 5 presents the data in terms of teacher's performance on the identified 5 key areas. Data shows that all teachers have received very satisfactory rating. This indicates that teachers are doing their responsibilities in providing quality education. Thus, very satisfactory is an indicator of being an effective teacher.

Table 6. Test of significant difference

Constructs	Mean	P value	Remarks	Decision
Self-Awareness	Teacher= 4.14 administrators= 4.32	0.295234	Not significant	Accept
Social-Awareness	Teacher= 4.132 Students= 4.432	0.004407	significant	Reject
Self-Management	Teacher= 4.044 Students= 4.57	0.00043	significant	Reject
Relationship-Management	Teacher= 4.268 Students= 4.492	0.18762	Not significant	Accept

Table 6 shows the significant difference on the teacher emotional intelligence. Data shows that aspects of self-awareness and relationship management were not significant, thus retail the null hypothesis in these aspects, while social awareness and self-

management were significant, thus we need reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that teachers and administrators have different level of emotional intelligence.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be noted that teachers have strong motivation and willingness as perceived by the administrators, and among all aspects of emotional intelligence, administrators perceived that teacher have enough self-management that dealt in times of difficulties. Moreover, teachers' performance on the identified 5 key areas were very satisfactory, thus, it is a strong predictor of teacher's awareness on their level of intelligence. Overall, finding suggest that although teachers have high level of emotional intelligence, low self-regulation and lack of accountability were seen as one of the teachers' weaknesses.

References

- Andriani, S., Kesumawati, N., & Kristiawan, M. (2018). The influence of the transformational leadership and work motivation on teachers' performance. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 7(7), 19-29.
- Altındağa, E., (2015). The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence of Managers, Innovative Corporate Culture and Employee Performance. 4th International Conference on Leadership, Technology, Innovation and Business Management. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Published by Elsevier Ltd. 210 (2015) 270 – 282.
- Akinsola, Mojeed K. et al. (2007) Correlates of Academic Procrastination and Mathematics Achievement of University Under Graduate Students.
- Allinder, R. M. (1994). The relationship between efficacy and the instructional practices of special education teachers and consultants. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 17, 86–95.
- Allinder, R. M. (1994). The relationship between efficacy and the instructional practices of special education teachers and consultants. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 17, 86–95.
- Armor, D., Conry-Oseguera, P., Cox, M., King, N., McDonnell, L., Pascal, A., Pauly, E., & Zellman, G. (1976). Analysis of the school preferred reading program in selected Los Angeles minority schools. Santa Monica, CA: Rand Corporation.
- Ashton, P. T., & Webb. Making a Difference: Teachers Sense of efficacy and Students Achievement. New York: Longman, 1986.
- Baytiyeh, H. (2018). Online learning during post-earthquake school closures. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*.
- Brunning, R. H., Schraw, G. J., Norby, M. M., & Ronning, R. R. (2004). *Cognitive psychology and instruction*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Cannella, G. S., & Reif, J. C. (1994). Preparing teachers for cultural diversity: Constructivist orientations. *Action in Teacher Education*, 26(3), 37–45. *Handbook of research on teaching*. (3rd ed., pp. 255-296). New York: Macmillan.
- Coladarci, T. (1992) Teachers' sense of efficacy and commitment to teaching. *Journal of Experimental Education*, 60(4), 323–37.

- Darling-Hammond, L. (2000). Teacher quality and student achievement: A review of the state policy evidence. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 8(1), 2–8.
- Eden, D., & Kinnar, J. (1991). Modeling Galatea: Boosting self-efficacy to increase volunteering. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(6), 773–780.
- Eden, D., & Kinnar, J. (1991). Modeling Galatea: Boosting self-efficacy to increase volunteering.
- Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Educational Technology. Jerusalem, M., & Mittag, W., (1995). Self-efficacy in stressful life transitions. In Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall. Bobbett, J. (2001) School culture, teacher efficacy, and decision making in demonstrably effective and ineffective schools. Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, Louisiana State University.
- Fall 2003 21 Gist, M. E., Schwoerer, C., & Rosen, G. (1989). Effects of alternative training methods on self-efficacy and performance in computer software training. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74(6), 884–891.
- Feistritz, C. E. (1999). Professional development opportunities for teachers. Washington, DC: Senate Committee on Health, Education, Labor and Pensions.
- Fullan, M. J. (1991). The new meaning of educational change. New York: Teachers College Press.
- G. S., & Reif, J. C. (1994). Preparing teachers for cultural diversity: Constructivist orientations. *Action in Teacher Education*, 26(3), 37–45. Coladarci, T. (1992) Teachers' sense of efficacy and commitment to teaching. *Journal of Experimental Education*, 60(4), 323–37.
- Garet, M. S., Birman, B. F., Porter, A. C., Desimone, L., Herman, R., & Yoon, K. S. (1999). Designing effective professional development: Lessons from the Eisenhower program. Jessup, MD: U.S. Department of Education.
- Gist, M. E., Bavetta, A. G., & Stevens, C. K. (1990). Transfer training method: Its influence on skill generalization, skill repetition, and performance level. *Personnel Psychology*, 43, 501–523.
- Gouchenour, T. (1977). The albatross. In D Batchelder & E. Warner (Eds.), *Beyond experience: The experiential approach to cross-cultural education* (pp. 131–136).
- Graham, S., & Weiner, B. Theories and Principles of Motivation. In D.C. Berliner & R.C. Calfee (Eds). *Handbook of Educational Psychology*. (New York: Simon & Schuster Macmillan), 1996.
- Guskey, T. R., (1988). Teacher efficacy, self-concept, and attitudes toward the implementation of instructional innovation. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 4(1), 63–69.
- Hani, J., Czerniak, C., & Lumpe, A. (1996). Teacher beliefs and intentions regarding the implementation of science education reform strands. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 33(9), 971–993
- Jacobs, J. W., & Dempsey, J. V. (1993). Simulation and gaming: Fidelity, feedback and motivation. In J. V. Dempsey and G. C. Sales (Eds.), *Interactive instruction and feedback* (pp. 197–229).
- Margot, K. C., & Kettler, T. (2019). Teachers' perception of STEM integration and education: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of STEM education*, 6(1), 1-16.
- Miao, C., Humphrey, R. H., & Qian, S. (2018). A cross-cultural meta-analysis of how leader emotional intelligence influences subordinate task performance and organizational citizenship behavior. *Journal of World Business*, 53(4), 463-474.

- Musa, S., & Ziatdinov, R. (2012). Features and Historical Aspects of the Philippines Educational System. *European journal of contemporary education*, 2(2), 155-176.
- Miles, M. (1995). Foreword. In T. R. Guskey and M. Huberman (Eds.), *Professional development in education: new paradigms and practices* (pp. vii–ix). New York: Teachers College Press.
- Mohamad, M., et al., (2016). Emotional Intelligence and Job Performance: A Study Among. Educational systems around the world have rapidly experiencing changes and reforms, impacting to teachers' job performance. 35 (2016) 674 – 682. Available online at www.sciencedirect.com.
- Palmer, P. J. (2017). *The courage to teach: Exploring the inner landscape of a teacher's life*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Ross, J. A., Hogaboam-Gray, A., & Hannay, L. (2001). Effects of teacher efficacy on computer skills and computer cognitions of Canadian students in K–3. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association.
- Seattle. Saks, A. M. (1995). Longitudinal field investigation of the moderating and mediating effects of self-efficacy on the relationship between training and newcomer adjustment. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 80, 221–22.
- Symaco, L. P., & Tee, M. Y. (2019). Social responsibility and engagement in higher education: Case of the ASEAN. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 66, 184-192
- Shahhosseini, M., et al., (2015). The Role of Emotional Intelligence on Job Performance. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. Centre for Promoting Ideas, USA. Vol. 3 No. 21; www.ijbssnet.com.
- Tejero E. (2004), *Thesis and Dissertation Writing: A Modular Approach*, (Manila: National Bookstore, 2004), p.36.

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